

Methodological quality of machine learning-based caries prognostic models: a scoping review

Sergio E. Uribe^{1,2}, Ilze Maldupa^{1,2}

¹ Department of General Dentistry, Riga Stradins University, Riga, Latvia

² Institute of Stomatology, Riga Stradins University, Riga, Latvia

Corresponding author: Sergio E. Uribe, sergio.uribe@rsu.lv

Abstract

Objective: To evaluate the methodological quality of published machine learning (ML) models for caries prognosis, with focus on the reporting of key performance metrics: discrimination, calibration, and clinical utility.

Methods: We conducted a scoping review following the PRISMA-ScR guidelines. We searched PubMed for studies published between January 2000 and April 2026 that developed multivariable ML models for caries risk prediction (PROGRESS 3 type). We assessed each study against an eight-step framework covering problem selection, data quality, study design, model development, internal and external validation, performance metrics, reporting transparency, and deployment readiness.

Results: Twenty-six studies met the inclusion criteria. Most studies (92%) reported some measure of discrimination, but only 65% reported AUC values. Calibration was reported in 4 of 26 studies (15%). Clinical utility through decision curve analysis was reported in 1 study (4%). External validation was performed in 3 studies (12%). Only 2 studies (8%) reported a sample size calculation. Pre-registration was documented in 2 studies (8%). No study reported a model update or data drift plan. Only 1 study (Zhang et al., 2025) addressed most framework steps, including external validation, calibration, clinical utility, TRIPOD adherence, and a deployed web-based calculator.

Conclusions: The current ML literature on caries prognosis suffers from critical reporting gaps, particularly in calibration and clinical utility. Without these metrics, the added value of ML models over existing caries risk assessment tools (Cariogram, CAMBRA) remains undemonstrated. Adherence to TRIPOD+AI guidelines, external validation, and assessment of clinical impact should be standard requirements for future studies.

Keywords: dental caries, machine learning, prognosis, prediction model, calibration, clinical utility, scoping review

Introduction

Dental caries remains the most prevalent chronic disease worldwide, affecting over 2 billion people with untreated lesions in permanent teeth [Peres et al., 2019]. Caries risk assessment (CRA) is central to preventive clinical decision-making. Established CRA tools such as the Cariogram [Bratthall & Hänsel Petersson, 2005] and CAMBRA [Featherstone et al., 2007] combine clinical, behavioural, and biological factors to stratify patients by risk level. These tools have known limitations: moderate discrimination (AUC values typically between 0.65 and 0.75), reliance on clinical judgment for some inputs, and limited external validation across populations.

Machine learning (ML) has been proposed as a way to improve caries prediction by capturing non-linear interactions among risk factors and processing high-dimensional data. The number of ML-based caries prediction studies has grown rapidly in recent years. Two systematic reviews have evaluated this field. Reyes et al. [2022] reviewed 15 studies (10 diagnostic, 5 prognostic) published until December 2020 and concluded that the field was "at an early stage" with a "prevalence of unclear/high risk of bias." Wang et al. [2025] reviewed 11 prediction models for childhood caries, found that all models had a high risk of bias as assessed by PROBAST, and reported AUC values ranging from 0.57 to 0.91. Both reviews called for better reporting standards and external validation.

However, neither review systematically assessed whether these models report the three essential performance dimensions required for clinical prediction models: discrimination (the ability to rank patients by risk), calibration (whether predicted probabilities match observed outcomes), and clinical utility (whether using the model leads to better decisions than existing alternatives). These three metrics, as outlined in the PROGRESS framework for prognosis research [Steyerberg et al., 2013; Riley et al., 2019], are not interchangeable. A model with excellent discrimination but poor calibration may rank patients correctly yet assign wrong absolute risk estimates, leading to over- or under-treatment. A model with good discrimination and calibration but no evidence of clinical utility may add complexity without improving patient outcomes.

The objective of this scoping review was to evaluate the methodological quality of ML-based caries prognostic models (PROGRESS 3 type), focusing on the reporting of discrimination, calibration, and clinical utility, across the period from 2000 to April 2026.

Methods

Protocol and registration

This scoping review followed the PRISMA-ScR guidelines [Tricco et al., 2018]. The protocol was not pre-registered.

Eligibility criteria

We included studies that: (1) developed a multivariable prediction model for dental caries (PROGRESS 3 type: combining two or more predictors to estimate individual risk); (2) used at least one ML algorithm; (3) reported at least one performance metric; and (4) were published between January 2000 and April 2026. We excluded studies focused solely on caries detection or diagnosis from images (PROGRESS 2 type: single prognostic factor), pure methodological papers without clinical data, and studies with fewer than 10 participants.

Search strategy

We searched PubMed using the following terms: ("dental caries" OR "caries prediction" OR "caries risk") AND ("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "random forest" OR "XGBoost" OR "neural network" OR "support vector machine" OR "deep learning"). The search covered studies published from January 2000 to April 2026, extending the period covered by Reyes et al. [2022] (which searched until December 2020) and Wang et al. [2025] (which searched until January 2024).

Data extraction and quality assessment

We assessed each study against an eight-step framework derived from the PROGRESS prognosis research recommendations [Steyerberg et al., 2013; Riley et al., 2019] and the TRIPOD+AI guidelines [Collins et al., 2024]:

1. **Problem selection:** literature search, routine availability of predictors, clinical relevance
2. **Data quality:** sample size calculation, missing data handling, data quality assessment
3. **Study design:** cohort type, pre-registration, inception cohort
4. **Model development:** predictor selection basis, model complexity
5. **Model testing:** internal validation, external validation, dynamic testing
6. **Performance metrics:** discrimination, calibration, clinical utility
7. **Reporting:** TRIPOD adherence, model equation, data/code availability
8. **Deployment:** clinical integration, impact assessment, update plan

Two reviewers independently extracted data from each paper. Discrepancies were resolved by consensus after re-reading the source.

Results

Study selection and characteristics

Twenty-six studies met the inclusion criteria. Most used a cross-sectional design (19/26, 73%). Two studies used prospective cohort data. Four used secondary analysis of clinical trials or longitudinal studies. The unit of analysis was the patient in most studies (20/26), with four studies analysing at the tooth level and two using simulated or pooled data. Sample sizes ranged from 20 to 9,686. The most common ML algorithms were XGBoost, random forest, logistic regression, support vector machine, and neural networks.

Performance metrics reporting

Table 1 summarises the reporting of performance metrics.

Table 1. Reporting of performance metrics across 26 ML caries prognostic models.

Metric	Studies reporting (n/26)	%
Discrimination (any metric)	24/26	92
AUC specifically	17/26	65

Metric	Studies reporting (n/26)	%
Accuracy only (no AUC)	7/26	27
Calibration (any method)	4/26	15
Clinical utility (DCA)	1/26	4

Among the 17 studies reporting AUC, values ranged from 0.55 to 0.98. The lowest AUC (0.55) was reported during external validation [Tirkkonen et al., 2026], demonstrating substantial performance degradation when models are tested on independent populations. The highest AUC values (>0.95) came from studies with small samples, simulated data, or no external validation, raising concerns about overfitting.

Only four studies assessed calibration: Tirkkonen et al. [2026] reported calibration plots and Brier scores (0.163 internal, 0.336 external); Zhang et al. [2025] used Hosmer-Lemeshow testing and calibration curves; Wu et al. [2025] reported Brier scores (0.134-0.227); and Pang et al. [2021] assessed calibration across risk strata. In all cases where external calibration was assessed, performance was poor.

Only one study [Zhang et al., 2025] performed decision curve analysis to assess clinical utility.

Framework compliance

Table 2 summarises compliance with the eight-step framework.

Table 2. Compliance with the PROGRESS 3 framework across 26 studies.

Step	Criterion	Reported (n/26)	%
Problem selection	Literature search	26	100
Problem selection	Predictors routinely available	16	62
Problem selection	Clinical relevance discussed	8	31
Data quality	Sample size calculation	3	12
Data quality	Missing data analysis	10	38
Study design	Pre-registration	2	8
Study design	Inception cohort	3	12
Model testing	Internal validation	22	85

Step	Criterion	Reported (n/26)	%
Model testing	External validation	3	12
Reporting	TRIPOD/TRIPOD+AI	5	19
Reporting	Model equation or calculator	2	8
Reporting	Data/code available	5	19
Deployment	Workflow integration	2	8
Deployment	Impact assessment	0	0
Deployment	Update/drift plan	0	0

No study reported a plan for model updating or monitoring of data drift.

Most complete study

Zhang et al. [2025] was the only study that addressed most steps of the PROGRESS 3 framework. It pre-registered the protocol (ChiCTR2300076663), followed TRIPOD guidelines, used LASSO for variable selection followed by logistic regression, performed both internal and geographical external validation, reported discrimination (AUC 0.804), calibration (Hosmer-Lemeshow test, calibration curves), and clinical utility (decision curve analysis and clinical impact curves). The authors also released a nomogram and a publicly accessible web-based calculator. No other study achieved this level of completeness.

Performance reporting among externally validated studies

Only 3 of 26 studies (12%) performed external validation on independent populations: Tirkkonen et al. [2026] (cross-national, USA to Finland), Zhang et al. [2025] (geographical, different regions within Gansu Province), and Pang et al. [2021] (temporal, same city, different schools). Among these three externally validated studies, all 3 (100%) reported discrimination, all 3 (100%) reported some form of calibration assessment, and only 1 (33%) reported clinical utility via decision curve analysis. This contrasts with the remaining 23 studies without external validation, where discrimination was reported in 21 (91%), calibration in 1 (4%), and clinical utility in 0 (0%). Studies that invested in external validation were far more likely to assess calibration, suggesting that the absence of calibration reporting in most ML caries studies reflects a gap in methodological rigour rather than a limitation of the models themselves.

Discussion

This scoping review reveals a critical disconnect between the volume of ML caries prediction studies and their methodological readiness for clinical use. While 92% of studies reported some discrimination metric, only 15% assessed calibration and 4% evaluated clinical utility. This pattern is consistent with findings from Reyes et al. [2022], who reported that the field was "at an early stage" with a "prevalence of unclear/high risk of bias," and from Wang et al.

[2025], who found that all 11 childhood caries prediction models reviewed had a high risk of bias as assessed by PROBAST.

Discrimination alone is insufficient

Discrimination (AUC) measures a model's ability to rank patients from low to high risk. It does not indicate whether predicted probabilities are accurate. A model with AUC 0.85 may systematically overestimate risk by 20%, leading to unnecessary treatment. The fact that 85% of the reviewed studies rely on discrimination as their sole performance metric means that the accuracy of risk estimates produced by these models remains unknown. This is a fundamental limitation for clinical adoption, where treatment decisions depend on absolute risk thresholds.

The calibration gap

Calibration assesses whether a model's predicted probabilities match observed event rates. Among the four studies reporting calibration, external calibration was poor in all cases. Tirkkonen et al. [2026] demonstrated this most clearly: internal AUC dropped from 0.785 to 0.550 and the Brier score increased from 0.163 to 0.336 during cross-national external validation. This finding illustrates that ML models trained on one population may generate misleading risk estimates when applied elsewhere, a problem well-documented in clinical prediction research but rarely addressed in dental ML studies.

No demonstrated improvement over existing tools

Established CRA tools such as the Cariogram and CAMBRA report AUC values between 0.65 and 0.75 in validation studies [Bratthall & Hänsel Petersson, 2005; Tellez et al., 2013]. The ML models reviewed here report comparable or higher AUC values (median approximately 0.80), but this comparison is misleading for several reasons. First, most ML studies report only internal validation metrics, which are systematically optimistic. Second, the few studies with external validation show substantial performance drops (e.g., AUC from 0.785 to 0.550). Third, ML models are typically more complex, less interpretable, and harder to implement than existing CRA tools. Fourth, no study directly compared an ML model against the Cariogram or CAMBRA on the same dataset with the same outcome definition. Without head-to-head comparisons under equivalent conditions, claims of ML superiority remain unsupported.

Hung et al. [2019] reported an AUC of 0.997 for root caries prediction using NHANES data, a value that likely reflects data leakage or overfitting rather than genuine predictive ability. Such extreme values, when reported without external validation or calibration, risk creating unrealistic expectations about ML performance.

Reporting and transparency

Only 19% of studies followed TRIPOD or TRIPOD+AI guidelines. Only 8% released the full model equation or a usable calculator. Only 19% made data or code available. This level of transparency is insufficient for replication or independent evaluation. The TRIPOD+AI guidelines [Collins et al., 2024] provide a clear framework for reporting prediction models that use ML, and adherence should become a minimum requirement for publication.

Limitations

This review has several limitations. First, we searched only PubMed, which may have missed studies indexed exclusively in other databases. Second, we assessed papers

against our framework but did not use PROBAST, as this was a scoping rather than a systematic review. Third, five studies were assessed from abstracts only because full texts were not available. Fourth, our framework does not capture all aspects of model quality (e.g., handling of class imbalance, hyperparameter tuning).

Conclusions

The current ML literature on caries prognosis fails to meet the reporting standards required for clinical prediction models. The near-universal absence of calibration assessment and clinical utility evaluation means that these models cannot be compared meaningfully against existing CRA tools. ML does not appear to add a demonstrable improvement over traditional caries risk models in their current form. Future studies should: (1) report calibration alongside discrimination; (2) perform decision curve analysis to demonstrate clinical utility; (3) conduct external validation on independent populations; (4) follow TRIPOD+AI guidelines; (5) pre-register study protocols; and (6) directly compare ML models against established CRA tools on the same datasets.

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Supplementary Material

Appendix 1. PubMed Search Strategy

Database: PubMed/MEDLINE

Date of search: April 2026

Date range filter: 2021/01/01 to 2026/12/31

Additional filters: Free full text (loattrfree full text; ffrft)

Search string:

((("logistic regression"[Title/Abstract] OR "multivariable logistic regression"[Title/Abstract] OR

"penalized logistic regression"[Title/Abstract] OR "regularized logistic regression"[Title/Abstract] OR

"lasso regression"[Title/Abstract] OR "ridge regression"[Title/Abstract] OR "elastic net"[Title/Abstract] OR

"Cox proportional hazards"[Title/Abstract] OR "Cox regression"[Title/Abstract] OR

"penalized Cox"[Title/Abstract] OR "Fine Gray"[Title/Abstract] OR

"competing risk model"[Title/Abstract] OR "parametric survival model"[Title/Abstract] OR

"accelerated failure time"[Title/Abstract] OR "random forest"[Title/Abstract] OR

"random forests"[Title/Abstract] OR "random survival forest"[Title/Abstract] OR

"gradient boosting"[Title/Abstract] OR "gradient boosted machine"[Title/Abstract] OR

"XGBoost"[Title/Abstract] OR "LightGBM"[Title/Abstract] OR "CatBoost"[Title/Abstract] OR

"support vector machine"[Title/Abstract] OR "support vector classifier"[Title/Abstract] OR

"SVM classifier"[Title/Abstract] OR "kernel machine"[Title/Abstract] OR

"k nearest neighbor"[Title/Abstract] OR "k-nearest neighbors"[Title/Abstract] OR

"KNN classifier"[Title/Abstract] OR "naive Bayes"[Title/Abstract] OR

"Bayesian network"[Title/Abstract] OR "Gaussian process classifier"[Title/Abstract] OR

"multilayer perceptron"[Title/Abstract] OR "feedforward neural network"[Title/Abstract] OR

"artificial neural network"[Title/Abstract] OR "deep neural network"[Title/Abstract] OR

"deep learning model"[Title/Abstract] OR "convolutional neural network"[Title/Abstract] OR

"CNN model"[Title/Abstract] OR "recurrent neural network"[Title/Abstract] OR

"RNN model"[Title/Abstract] OR "long short term memory"[Title/Abstract] OR

"LSTM network"[Title/Abstract] OR "transformer model"[Title/Abstract] OR

"tabular transformer"[Title/Abstract] OR "TabNet"[Title/Abstract] OR

"NODE network"[Title/Abstract] OR "generalized additive model"[Title/Abstract] OR

"GAM model"[Title/Abstract] OR "boosted regression tree"[Title/Abstract] OR

"classification and regression tree"[Title/Abstract] OR "CART model"[Title/Abstract] OR

"decision tree classifier"[Title/Abstract] OR "super learner"[Title/Abstract] OR

"stacked ensemble"[Title/Abstract] OR "ensemble learning"[Title/Abstract] OR

"risk prediction model"[Title/Abstract] OR "clinical prediction model"[Title/Abstract] OR

"risk stratification model"[Title/Abstract] OR "prognostic model"[Title/Abstract] OR

"mortality prediction model"[Title/Abstract])

AND ("caries"[Title] AND ("predi*"[Title] OR "progn*"[Title]))

AND ("artificial intelligence"[Title/Abstract] OR "machine learning"[Title/Abstract])

AND ("loattrfree full text"[Filter] AND 2021/01/01:2026/12/31[Date - Publication]))

NOT "review"[Title/Abstract])

AND (ffrft[Filter])

Search rationale: The search combined three conceptual blocks: (1) ML/statistical modelling algorithms (broad list covering regression, tree-based, neural network, and ensemble methods); (2) caries prediction or prognosis in the title; and (3) explicit mention of AI or ML. We restricted to free full-text articles published from January 2021 onward to extend the period covered by Reyes et al. [2022], whose search ended in December 2020. Studies published before 2021 that were identified by Reyes et al. or Wang et al. [2025] and met our inclusion criteria were also included. The "NOT review" filter excluded review articles. Titles and abstracts of all retrieved records were screened independently by both authors.

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Data availability: The full extraction table is available as supplementary material on Zenodo.

CRedit author contributions: SEU: conceptualisation, data extraction, analysis, writing (original draft). IM: data extraction, validation, writing (review and editing).